

http://plugin67.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

Search | i<!doctype html>(Use /re/ syntax for regexp search)
2      <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4      <head>
5          <meta charset="UTF-8">
6          <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7          <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9          <title>Marketing Digital Tools &#8211; Agência de Mar
10 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
11 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
12 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
13     <script type="text/javascript">
14         window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https:\\/\\s.
15         !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
16     </script>
17     <style type="text/css">
18     img.wp-smiley,
19     img.emoji {
20         display: inline !important;
21         border: none !important;
22         box-shadow: none !important;
23         height: 1em !important;
24         width: 1em !important;
25         margin: 0 .07em !important;
26         vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
27         background: none !important;
28         padding: 0 !important;
29     }
30 </style>
31     <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
32 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://g
33 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
34 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='f
35 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http:
36 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-smallscreen-css' href=
37 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
38 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
39 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
40 </style>
41 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://plu
42 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plug
43 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>
44 @media (min-width: 1200px) {.tg-container{max-width: 1200px;}}
45 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, bli
46 </style>
47 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-woocommerce-style-css' href=
48 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-css' href='http://
49 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-animations-css' href='ht
50 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-frontend-css' href='http:
51 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-global-css' href='http://
52 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-post-24-css' href='http:
53 <link rel='stylesheet' id='google-fonts-1-css' href='https://
54 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-shared-0-css' href
55 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-solid-css' href
56 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-brands-css' hre
57 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin67.marketingd
58 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin67.marketingd
59 <link rel='https://api.w.org/' href='http://plugin67.marketing
60 <link rel="EditURI" type="application/rsd+xml" title="RSD" hre
61 <link rel="wlanifest" type="application/wlanifest+xml" hre
    
```

LocalBusiness

All (1)

LocalBusiness	PRÉ-	0 ERROS	1 AVISO
ID: http://plugin67.marketingdigitaltools.com/54B59928-D6BD-4073-ADA6-0486C3606013			
@type	LocalBusiness		
@id	http://plugin67.marketingdigitaltools.com/54B59928-D6BD-4073-ADA6-0486C3606013		
image	http://plugin67.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png		
url	http://plugin67.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
name	MARKeting Digital Tools		
description	Agência de Marketing Digital Ecommerce		
telephone	+351913824934		
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools		
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/		
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools		
address			
@type	PostalAddress		
streetAddress	Rua de Santo António de Contumil, 651		
addressLocality	Porto		
geo			
@type	GeoCoordinates		
longitude	-8.580057		
latitude	41.173869		
priceRange	O campo <i>priceRange</i> é recomendado. Forneça um valor, se disponível.		